

Fluorine containing Bioactive Heterocycles. Investigation of the Reactions of Fluorine containing 3-Hydrazino-5*H*-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles with Carbon Disulphide and Synthesis of 2,3-Dihydro-1-thioxo-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*c*]-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles as Antibacterial Agents

KRISHNA C. JOSHI*, ANSHU DANDIA and SUNITA BAWEJA

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

The reactions of fluorine containing 3-hydrazino-5*H*-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles (2) with carbon disulphide leading to the synthesis of novel 2,3-dihydro-1-thioxo-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*c*]-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles (3) was investigated. The direction of cyclisation was established on the basis of enhanced stability of angular product as compared to the linear product. Further, the alkylation of compound 3 with methyl iodide was studied, and position of alkyl substitution was assigned. The quaternisation of new system (3) was also observed under these reaction conditions. The compounds have been screened for antibacterial activity. Characterisation of the compounds has been done on the basis of elemental analyses, ir, pmr, ¹³C nmr, ¹⁹F nmr and mass spectral data.

AS part of our continued interest¹⁻³ on the orientation of cyclisation in the reaction of unsymmetric triazinoindole, we now report our studies on the reaction of fluorine containing 3-hydrazino-5*H*-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole.

The 1,2,4-triazole derivatives possess a wide range of interesting biological activities⁴. 3-Mercapto-1,2,4-triazole derivatives were noticed to display antimicrobial activity⁵. Various derivatives of 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*f*][1,2,4]triazine possess antitumor activity⁶. Besides, triazolotriazinoindoles are reported as active antiviral agents⁷.

The unusual physical and pigment properties of 2,3-diphenyl-10*H*-imidazo[1,2-*b*]-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole⁸ have aroused considerable interest and it was proposed to synthesise its structural analog, viz. triazolotriazinoindole. A literature survey reveals only one report⁹, mentioning the formation of 2,3-dihydro-3-thioxo-1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-*b*]-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole (3') in 70% yield and its pigment properties, but the compound was not recommended for use as dye because of its low colour intensity and instability towards alkalis. The fluorinated dyes are characterised by their stability and intense pigment properties in comparison to the non-fluorinated counterparts^{10,11}. Since no fluorinated analogs of 3' have been reported, it was considered of interest to synthesise fluorinated derivatives of 3' which may have enhanced pigment properties and can be used as dye. Further, by the alkylation of acidic group, the stability in base can be increased.

Moreover, it was noticed that no information is available on the various synthetic and biological aspects of 3'. In the various cyclisation reactions

of 3-hydrazino-5*H*-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole, there is some controversy about the structure of final product as the chances of cyclisation are equal both at N-4^{12,13} and N-2¹⁴. Rather surprisingly, this type of possibility in the reaction of 3-hydrazino-5*H*-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole with carbon disulphide has not received any attention.

In view of all these findings, we have investigated the reactions of fluorine containing 3-hydrazino-5*H*-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles and obtained orange coloured crystalline products, identified as 2,3-dihydro-1-thioxo-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*c*]-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles (3) having angular structure. Interestingly, in addition to the expected product, a shining white compound having long needle shaped crystals, was also isolated. However, structural assignment of this compound is still under investigation. Further, anticipating enhanced bioactivity and increased solubility of alkyl substituted derivatives, we have carried out the alkylation of compound 3.

Appropriate indole-2,3-diones were condensed with thiosemicarbazide to afford 3-thioxo-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole (1), which on treatment with hydrazine hydrate, yielded 3-hydrazino-5*H*-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole (2).

Since the compound 2 is unsymmetrical, it was expected that on cyclisation with carbon disulphide, it may yield 3 having an angular structure or alternatively 3' with linear structure or both depending upon the direction of cyclisation (Scheme 1). The modified reaction procedure⁹ has resulted in the formation of bright red coloured compounds in enhanced yields (85–90%). The compounds displayed characteristic ir absorptions at 3 350–3 180

Scheme 1

(NH), 1 620 (C=N) and 1 270 cm^{-1} (C=S). The pmr signals were observed in the region δ 6.88–7.85 (m, ArH), 8.8 (s, NH) and 9.85 (s, NH) ppm. Cyclisation was confirmed by the absence of absorption band corresponding to amino group and appearance of thione band in the ir spectra. In ^{13}C nmr spectra, four aromatic carbons (CH) were observed as doublets at δ 112.63, 122.78, 123.51 and 134.12 ppm and the two aromatic carbons (C) as singlets at 116.12 and 149.37 ppm. Two carbons of triazino-[5,6-*b*]indole were observed as singlet at δ 142.45, 146.92 and 146.14 ppm. Characteristic thione carbon (C=S) appeared in the downfield region at δ 159.99 ppm. The mass spectrum of the final product **3c** has shown M^+ at m/z 260 (100%) and **3d** at m/z 310 (22%).

However, the spectral data could not convincingly decide if the product was angular (**3**) or linear (**3'**). The mode of cyclisation will be governed by the stability of the product formed^{15,16} and similar reports in the literature favour formation of a more benzenoid structure^{1,17}. Thus, in the present case, the formation of angular product involving cyclisation at N-4 should be preferred. In this structure, the 10 π -electron system, i.e. aromatic character of the indole ring is preserved and is stabilised by high resonance energy.

The preferential formation of angular product could be supported on the basis of extended conjugation in this structure and enhanced nucleophilicity of N-4 in comparison to N-2. Thus the nitrogen at N-4 will attack thione carbon of carbon disulphide giving energetically active intermediate

which undergoes protropic changes followed by the loss of H_2S to give **3**. Moreover, in angular structure, the C=S group comes in proximity to NH, thus hydrogen bonded (chelated) six-membered cyclic structure accounts for the stability of angular product. Further support has been obtained by isotopic studies done by Messmer *et al.*¹⁸ in similar cases. Thus in view of all these considerations, an angular structure has been assigned to product **3**.

The alkylation of this new ring system was thought of interest as several sites are available for alkylation. Alkylation of **3a**, accomplished with excess of methyl iodide and sodium acetate, resulted in the formation of three products **3b**, **4** and **5** which were separated by column chromatography.

The structure of **3b**, obtained in 20% yield, was assigned unequivocally by comparing its chemical and physical properties with those of the product obtained by the reaction of 5-methyl-3-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole with carbon disulphide. The identity was established by m.m.p. and superimposable ir and pmr spectra.

Compound **4** was obtained in 42% yield and its structure was assigned on the basis of spectral data, as in ir spectrum, absorption bands corresponding to NH and C=S disappeared and in pmr spectrum two characteristic methyl signals were observed at δ 2.78 (3H, s, S- CH_3) and 3.38 (5H, s, N- CH_3) in agreement with their environment. Further support was obtained by mass spectrum, as the molecular ion peak M^+ (m/z 270) exactly corresponded to the molecular weight of **4**.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2,3-DIHYDRO-1-THIOXO-1,2,4-TRIAZOLO[3,4-c]-1,2,4-TRIAZINO[5,6-b]INDOLES (3a-e)

Compd. no.	R	R ¹	R ²	R ³	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)	
								N	S
3a	H	H	H	H	368 ^a	88	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₆ S	—	—
3b	OH ₂	H	H	H	342	90	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₆ S	32.72 (32.81)	12.64 (12.60)
3c	H	H	F	H	346	89	C ₁₀ H ₇ FN ₆ S	32.46 (32.30)	12.16 (12.30)
3d	H	H	H	OF ₂	388	85	C ₁₁ H ₇ F ₂ N ₆ S	27.24 (27.09)	10.48 (10.32)
3e	H	F	H	H	340	86	C ₁₀ H ₇ FN ₆ S	32.16 (32.30)	12.38 (12.30)

^aLit.⁸ 358°.

Compound 5, obtained in 28% yield, was identified as quaternary salt on the basis of spectral data, qualitative test and some earlier reports on quaternisation of triazoles¹⁹, fused triazoles^{19,20} and 1,2,4-triazole-3-thione²¹ under similar reaction conditions. The pmr spectrum of this compound displayed three signals at δ 2.85 (3H, s, S-CH₃), 3.40 (3H, s, N-CH₃) and 3.58 (3H, s, N-CH₃) indicating the presence of three methyl groups. Further, in the mass spectrum, M⁺ was observed at m/z 285, which supports the presence of three methyl groups. Apparently, in compound 3a, there are only two labile hydrogens available for substitution, therefore, it was a problem to assign the position of third methyl group. However, it was noticed that compound obtained is water-soluble and gives the qualitative test for iodide ion. Besides, its tlc behaviour is rather surprising as the spot does not move on the tlc plate even in the polar solvents. Further, it has been reported that 1,2,4-triazoles carrying a variety of substituents in the 3- and 5-positions including 1-aryl and alkyl groups react with methyl iodide to give quaternary salt^{19,21}. Similarly, fused triazole, viz. triazoloquinoline were reported to undergo quaternary salt formation under similar reaction conditions^{19,20}. Thus, in view of these observations, it is assumed that one methyl group attaches at the tertiary nitrogen resulting in the formation of a quaternary salt. The position of methyl group appears to be at N-2 of triazole ring, in view of different possible resonating forms²², electron density calculations²³ supported by literature survey¹⁹, and the compound has thus been characterised as 5.

Further, the alkylation of 3b gave a mixture of two products, which were separated by column chromatography and identified as 4 and 5 on the basis of m.m.p. and superimposable ir and pmr spectra. The presence and position of fluorine was confirmed by ¹⁹F nmr spectra. Fluorine attached at 5- and 6-positions of indole ring was observed at δ -115 and -112 ppm respectively and 4-trifluoromethyl group was observed at δ -62.96 ppm.

Physical and analytical data of compounds 3a-e are presented in table 1.

Evaluation of antibacterial activity: All the compounds were screened against gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus albus* and gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*. Ampicillin was used as standard strain for comparison. The Kirby Bauer method²⁴ was used in screening the ethanolic solution of compounds for antibacterial activity. The area of inhibition of growth of bacteria, produced by diffusion of compounds from disc into the surrounding medium was measured. The results are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Zone of inhibition (mm)*		
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. albus</i>	Standard strain
3a	R	8 (P.S.)	8 (P.S.)
3b	14 (P.S.)	8 (P.S.)	14 (S)
3c	14 (S)	R	12 (P.S.)
3d	8 (P.S.)	10 (P.S.)	R
3e	R	12 (P.S.)	8 (P.S.)
4	16 (S)	12 (P.S.)	8 (P.S.)
5	12 (P.S.)	14 (S)	10 (P.S.)

*R=Resistant range, 8 mm zone; P.S.=partial sensitive range, 8-12 mm; S=sensitive range, 12 mm per disc.

The results indicate that the introduction of alkyl group and fluorine substitution increases the antibacterial activity against both gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer, (89.55 MHz) using TMS as external reference and DMSO-d₆ or TFA as solvents, ¹⁹F nmr spectra on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer (84.25 MHz) taken in DMSO-d₆ using hexafluorobenzene (at δ -162.9 ppm) as external reference, and mass spectra on MS-30 and MS-50 Kratos spectrometer operating at an ionisation potential of 70 eV.

3-Thioxo-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-b]indoles (1a-e)²⁵: A mixture of appropriate indole-2,3-dione (0.05 mol), thiosemicarbazide (0.55 mol) and

K_2CO_3 (0.075 mol) in water was refluxed for 7–8 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered and acidified with glacial acetic acid to give the desired compound which was recrystallised from ethanol.

3-Hydrazino-5H-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-b]indoles (2a–e)^{1,2}: Appropriate 3-thioxo-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-b]indole (1; 0.05 mol) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (30–40 ml) for 4–5 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and filtered. The precipitate was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol to give the desired compound.

2,3-Dihydro-1-thioxo-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-c]-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-b]indole (3a–e): The compounds were synthesised by the modified method³ in 85–90% yield. A mixture of 3-hydrazino-5H-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-b]indole (2; 0.01 mol) and carbon disulphide (5 ml) in anhydrous pyridine (30 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. On cooling the reaction mixture, the resulting bright orange-red coloured crystalline solid was washed with acetone and recrystallised from DMF to give the desired compound (Table 1).

Methylation of 2,3-dihydro-1-thioxo-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-c]-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-b]indole (3a): A mixture of 3a (0.01 mol) and CH_3I (3 ml) and CH_3COONa (0.04 g) in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into water. The precipitated compound was filtered and dried. Tlc analysis of the crude compound indicated the presence of three major components which were separated by column chromatography. The initial eluting solvents was benzene–ethyl acetate (4 : 1, v/v). The polarity of the solvent was increased to ethyl acetate–methanol (1 : 4, v/v) for the final fractions.

The first component was obtained from the fraction benzene–ethyl acetate (1 : 4, v/v) as dark red coloured crystalline compound whose chemical and physical properties were identical to those of 3b (0.05 g, 20%), m.p. 342°.

An orange red crystalline compound was obtained from the fraction ethyl acetate–methanol (4 : 1, v/v) and identified as 4 (1.13 g, 42%), m.p. 264° (Found: N, 31.25; S, 11.72. $C_{12}H_{10}N_6S$ requires: N, 31.11; S, 11.85%).

The third compound was obtained from the fraction ethyl acetate–methanol (1 : 4, v/v) as bright yellow coloured crystalline powder and identified as 5 (0.79 g, 28%), m.p. 286°.

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